

SUBJECT COORDINATORS AS TEACHER SUPPORT AND PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT FACILITATORS

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Subject Coordinators as Teacher Support and Professional Development Facilitators

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Abstract

This study examined the role of subject coordinators in providing teacher support and facilitating professional development within the Schools Division of Escalante City using a mixed-methods approach. The qualitative phase involved ten (10) subject coordinators, selected based on their responsibilities, educational qualifications, and experience. The findings revealed four key themes: (1) Teacher Support for Effective Curriculum Implementation and Student Success, highlighting coordinators' efforts to align instructional practices with curriculum standards and improve student outcomes; (2) Empowering Teacher Growth through Targeted and Collaborative Professional Development, emphasizing collaborative and personalized learning opportunities for teachers; (3) Hurdles to Effective Teacher Support and Professional Development, identifying challenges such as inconsistent feedback, limited resources, and difficulties in supporting assessment and reporting processes; and (4) Fostering Continuous Growth and Empowerment in Education, underscoring the importance of reflective teaching practices and continuous professional development. The quantitative phase involved 339 subject coordinators from 41 schools, with 181 participants selected through stratified random sampling. Quantitative results revealed a mean score of 3.60 for challenges, including time constraints, overlapping responsibilities, and resource limitations. Meanwhile, opportunities for professional development were perceived positively, with an overall mean score of 4.14, reflecting strong engagement in professional learning, inclusive strategies, and alignment with classroom realities. These findings highlight a dual dynamic where significant challenges coexist with promising opportunities. Addressing these obstacles while leveraging existing strengths can enhance teacher effectiveness and professional growth. The study recommends improving time management, optimizing resource allocation, and strengthening collaboration among subject coordinators to foster a more supportive and empowering educational environment.

Keywords: *subject coordinators, teacher support, professional development, curriculum implementation, educational effectiveness, assessment and reporting*

Introduction

In the evolving educational landscape, subject coordinators have become pivotal in enhancing the quality of teaching and learning. Their multifaceted responsibilities encompass providing instructional support, facilitating professional development, and ensuring teachers have the necessary resources and guidance (Smith & Brown, 2020). Understanding the role and impact of subject coordinators is crucial for improving educational practices and outcomes.

The Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines has increasingly recognized the importance of subject coordinators in supporting high-quality education. DepEd Order No. 13, s. 2024 emphasizes strengthening the roles of subject coordinators as facilitators of continuous professional development and instructional leadership. This order underscores the expectation that subject coordinators will actively assist teachers in adopting innovative teaching methods, aligning their instructional strategies with national standards, and adapting to the unique needs of their students.

Additionally, DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017, which introduced the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), provides a framework that subject coordinators can use to support teachers in meeting the expectations for effective teaching and professional growth. The PPST outlines key competencies and performance indicators for teachers at different career stages—from beginning to distinguished—emphasizing curriculum content knowledge, planning, assessment, and community involvement. Subject coordinators are essential in guiding teachers in these areas, helping them understand and achieve the standards outlined in the PPST. They provide professional development, resources, and ongoing feedback to help teachers align their instructional practices with the PPST, ultimately aiming to improve teaching quality and student outcomes.

Despite the broad recognition of the role of subject coordinators, there are significant gaps in understanding their specific roles and impacts within localized contexts like the Schools Division of Escalante City. Subject coordinators in Escalante City face various challenges, including limited resources, varying levels of teacher engagement, and the need to balance multiple responsibilities. Understanding these challenges is crucial for developing effective support systems and interventions. There is also a need for more structured and targeted professional development programs to enhance the skills and effectiveness of subject coordinators (Smith & Brown, 2020). Identifying gaps in current practices is essential for improving support for both coordinators and teachers.

While general research on subject coordinators is extensive, focused studies on their roles in specific settings are limited (Davis & Thompson, 2022). This study aims to address these gaps by providing a detailed examination of the impact of subject coordinators in this local setting. Existing research often addresses professional development in a broad sense but may not fully capture the specific needs and challenges faced by coordinators and teachers in diverse regions (Aguirre & Bargo, 2020). This study offers insights into

how professional development can be more effectively tailored to support coordinators and teachers.

This study is justified as it aims to provide actionable insights to improve instructional support and professional development practices in the Schools Division of Escalante City. The findings will inform local educational policies and practices, offering recommendations for optimizing the roles of subject coordinators and designing more effective professional development programs. By addressing local needs and contributing to the broader body of knowledge, the research will enhance the effectiveness of subject coordinators, ultimately benefiting teachers in the region. Understanding the roles of subject coordinators is essential for grasping their impact on educational practices and outcomes, filling existing gaps in the literature, and providing valuable insights to improve the quality of education.

Research Questions

This study aims to investigate the role of subject coordinators as teacher support and professional development facilitators in schools. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of Subject Coordinators in providing teacher support and facilitating professional development in school?
2. What is the extent of teacher support provided by the subject coordinators?
3. What is the extent of professional development facilitation by the subject coordinators to teachers?
4. What is the extent of challenges encountered by subject coordinators in providing teacher support and facilitating professional development activities?
5. What is the extent of opportunities perceived by subject coordinators in providing teacher support and facilitating professional development activities?
6. Based on the findings of the study, what intervention program will be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a mixed methods research design, specifically an exploratory sequential approach, to investigate the role of subject coordinators in providing teacher support and facilitating professional development within schools. The research began with a qualitative phase to explore the experiences of subject coordinators as provider of teacher support and facilitator of professional development. It also capture nuanced perspectives and challenges in their roles. Following this, a quantitative phase was conducted to systematically describe the extent of teacher support provided, facilitation of professional development activities, challenges, and opportunities.

The mixed methods design was deemed suitable for examining the complex roles of subject coordinators, as it captured both objective and subjective aspects, providing a comprehensive understanding of the research phenomenon (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). This approach facilitated triangulation (Flick, 2018), enhancing research credibility by corroborating findings from one method with the other.

By integrating quantitative and qualitative data, this study aimed to provide a holistic view crucial for developing effective strategies to enhance teacher support and professional development. This contextual understanding was essential for developing targeted recommendations to enhance the effectiveness of subject coordinators.

Participants

The research began with a qualitative phase by conducting interviews. In alignment with Creswell's (2014) recommendation for phenomenological research, a sample of three to ten participants was selected. In this study, ten (10) subject coordinators from various schools were chosen based on the following inclusion criteria, (a) having responsibilities related to teacher support and professional development, (b) holding or pursuing a master's or doctorate degree, and (c) having at least three years of experience in their current role. This approach was expected to achieve data saturation and effectively capture the essence of the coordinators' experiences and challenges across different school contexts (Guest et al., 2006).

Following the qualitative phase, the research proceeded with a quantitative phase employing stratified random sampling. With a population of 339 subject area coordinators distributed across 41 schools (14 secondary, 25 elementary, and 2 integrated), the goal was to select a sample of 181 coordinators. The population was divided into three strata based on school type: secondary schools, elementary schools, and integrated schools. The sample size for each stratum was calculated proportionally, with approximately 61 coordinators selected from secondary schools, 111 from elementary schools, and 9 from integrated schools.

To ensure a representative sample, random sampling was conducted within each stratum. Coordinators were randomly selected using methods such as random number generation, ensuring an unbiased and systematic selection process. This approach was intended to yield a sample that proportionally represented all three school types, reducing selection bias and enhancing the study's external validity. Ultimately, this method enabled the research to make reliable generalizations about the broader population of subject coordinators engaged in teacher support and professional development activities within schools (Creswell, 2014).

Instrument

This mixed methods study utilized two distinct research instruments to gather data for both the qualitative and quantitative phases. In the qualitative phase, in-depth interviews were conducted using a researcher-developed interview guide to explore the experiences of subject coordinators in providing teacher support and facilitating professional development. The guide was crafted following established qualitative research methods and underwent a rigorous pilot testing and refinement process. It was reviewed by the researcher's advisor and a panel of experts to ensure alignment with research objectives, effectiveness in eliciting detailed insights, and overall clarity.

In the quantitative phase, a researcher-made questionnaire was designed to capture data on the extent of teacher support and facilitation of professional development activities, as well as the challenges and opportunities faced by subject coordinators in these roles. The questionnaire, which consisted of two parts, was tailored to the study's context based on initial data gathered during the qualitative interviews. The instrument is divided into four sections which include the extent of teacher support, the extent of professional development facilitation, the extent of challenges encountered by subject coordinators, and the extent of opportunities perceived by subject coordinators. The questionnaire underwent a validation process including expert review and pilot testing to ensure content validity. This comprehensive approach ensured that the research instruments effectively captured both qualitative and quantitative data, providing a holistic understanding of the roles of subject coordinators.

Procedure

Before conducting the interviews and surveys, the researcher obtained permission from the appropriate school authorities, including the School Division Superintendent and the respective school heads of the participating schools. Following this approval, participants were selected based on predetermined criteria, and consent was sought from each participant. Once contact with the participants was confirmed, face-to-face interviews were scheduled. During these interviews, the researcher explained the purpose of the study and the measures taken to ensure confidentiality and obtain informed consent from the participants. The interviews were conducted individually, with participants encouraged to share their experiences and insights regarding their roles in teacher support and professional development. The researcher remained attentive and flexible, adjusting the duration of the interviews as needed to facilitate a thorough exploration of the participants' experiences. Interview locations were chosen to ensure participants' comfort, privacy, and a conducive environment for effective data collection.

For the quantitative phase, an online data collection method using Google Forms was employed. This approach offered several benefits, including potentially higher response rates compared to traditional paper-based surveys. Furthermore, by not collecting personally identifiable information, the survey ensured participant anonymity. The organization of the data gathering procedures for both qualitative and quantitative phases aimed to provide a clear and coherent overview of the research methodology, ensuring robust and reliable data collection for the study on subject coordinators' roles in teacher support and professional development.

Data Analysis

To address the research questions and analyze qualitative data in this study, Creswell's (2014) thematic analysis approach was adopted. This systematic process involved coding data by categorizing specific statements into themes that represented the roles and experiences of subject coordinators in teacher support and professional development (Creswell, 2014). The study followed Creswell's (2014) six-step process for conducting qualitative data analysis. Initially, the researcher organized and transcribed the collected data by carefully listening to audio recordings of each interview. This immersion in the participants' discourse helped capture the nuances of their experiences. The data was then reviewed comprehensively to understand its significance, with notes annotated on transcript margins to capture general impressions and aid in categorization.

Data organization proceeded through coding, where sections were bracketed and assigned category labels, often reflecting participants' own language. The researcher then re-examined the data to merge themes into overarching concepts, integrating similar clusters to form second-order themes. The coding process generated detailed descriptions and themes, providing insights into the subject coordinators' roles. Codes related to these descriptions were developed to identify a limited number of themes for analysis, typically between five to seven. The final analysis involved segmenting and labeling the descriptions and themes within the data, creating a qualitative narrative. This narrative included a chronological account of events and an exploration of interconnected themes. Findings were interpreted through a discussion of "lessons learned," influenced by the researcher's cultural background and experiences, as outlined by Lincoln and Guba (1985), cited in Creswell (2014).

To ensure the trustworthiness of the qualitative findings, Creswell's (1998) framework for evaluating trustworthiness was utilized. The criteria included: The first criterion was credibility, ensuring the research accurately reflected the subject coordinators' experiences. The use of standardized qualitative methods, such as structured interviews, strengthened credibility by capturing detailed and reliable insights. The second criterion was transferability, considering the generalizability of findings to other contexts. Providing additional information about participants and their work environments helped assess the transferability of the findings to similar settings. The third criterion was dependability, evaluating the consistency of research methods and the potential for replication. The use of a standardized interview guide supported dependability by minimizing researcher bias and allowing for replication of the study. The fourth criterion was confirmability, ensuring the neutrality of research interpretations and minimizing bias. Member checking, where

participants reviewed and confirmed the researcher's interpretations, enhanced confirmability by verifying the accuracy of the findings. Audit trail was also conducted by an expert in qualitative research in order to verify the accuracy of the themes emerging from this study.

For the quantitative phase, the researcher used mean scores as a statistical tool to present survey results. This approach provided a clear overview of the extent of teacher support and professional development activities facilitated by subject coordinators, as well as extent of challenges and extent of opportunities in these role highlighting key patterns and trends in the data.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were meticulously integrated throughout both the qualitative and quantitative phases of this study to uphold participants' rights and mitigate potential harm. Central to this approach was the principle of informed consent, where participants received comprehensive information about the study's purpose, procedures, and their rights before data collection began.

In the qualitative phase, participants were assured of their voluntary participation in face-to-face interviews, emphasizing their freedom to withdraw at any point without repercussion. Similarly, in the quantitative phase, an informed consent statement was presented at the onset of the survey, requiring participants to acknowledge their consent before proceeding. Anonymity and confidentiality were prioritized in both phases, employing measures such as coding and de-identifying data to protect participant privacy.

Strict data security protocols were followed, including secure storage and transmission of data in compliance with Google Forms' data security practices. Participants were explicitly informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty, ensuring that participation was entirely voluntary and free from coercion. Transparency was maintained throughout the study, with clear explanations provided regarding data usage and dissemination, ensuring participants were aware of how their information would be handled.

By prioritizing these ethical imperatives, the study aimed to generate valuable insights into the roles of subject coordinators as facilitators of teacher support and professional development while upholding the dignity and autonomy of its participants.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings from both qualitative and quantitative analyses conducted in the study. Qualitative data were gathered through in-depth interviews with 10 subject coordinators, providing rich insights into their experiences, challenges, and the support they offer to teachers. Concurrently, quantitative data were collected via surveys administered to 181 subject coordinators in the Schools Division of Escalante City, offering a broader perspective on their roles and the impact of their support on educational practices. By integrating these two methodologies, this study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the contributions of subject coordinators to teacher development and the overall quality of education in the division.

Qualitative Interpretation of Results

The qualitative component of this study delves into the experiences and perceptions of subject coordinators within the Schools Division of Escalante City, providing an enriched understanding of their roles and the complexities of supporting teachers. Through in-depth interviews with 10 subject coordinators, four key themes emerged that offer insights into their responsibilities and the challenges they face in fostering effective teaching practices.

The first theme, Teacher Support for Effective Curriculum Implementation and Student Success, highlights the coordinators' efforts to provide guidance, resources, and feedback that help teachers implement the curriculum effectively and achieve positive student outcomes. This theme aligns with previous findings by Kirtman (2009) and Korkmaz and Altun (2019), who emphasized the instructional leadership role of coordinators in advancing both teacher and student success.

The second theme, Empowering Teacher Growth through Targeted and Collaborative Professional Development, reflects the coordinators' commitment to providing tailored professional development opportunities that meet teachers' specific needs and promote a culture of collaboration. This theme underscores the coordinators' role in fostering continuous learning and shared growth among teachers, echoing their dedication to teacher development as an ongoing priority.

The third theme, Hurdles to Effective Teacher Support and Professional Development, captures the barriers that coordinators encounter, such as resource limitations, time constraints, and the need to align professional development initiatives with diverse teacher needs. These challenges resonate with findings by Durrant and Holden (2006), who documented similar obstacles, suggesting that effectively addressing these issues is essential for optimizing the coordinators' impact.

The final theme, Fostering Continuous Growth and Empowerment in Education, represents the coordinators' vision of creating a sustainable framework for long-term teacher support. This theme reveals a commitment to empowering teachers to continuously refine their instructional practices through ongoing support and professional growth opportunities.

Together, these themes illustrate the multifaceted contributions of subject coordinators to establishing a supportive and collaborative teaching environment, while also pinpointing areas where additional resources and training could further enhance their effectiveness.

This qualitative analysis complements the quantitative findings, offering a comprehensive view of the dynamics between coordinators and teachers and underscoring the importance of coordinated support strategies to strengthen educational practices within the division.

Theme 1: Teacher Support for Effective Curriculum Implementation and Student Success

The data reveals that subject coordinators play a vital role in supporting teachers with curriculum implementation, ultimately enhancing student learning outcomes. Teachers emphasized coordinators' assistance in translating curriculum standards into practical classroom activities. Five key areas of coordinator support emerged, discussed below as subthemes: (a) curriculum oversight and lesson planning, (b) assessment design and technical help, (c) classroom observation and feedback, (d) mentorship for new teachers, and (e) communication and knowledge sharing.

In curriculum oversight and lesson planning, coordinators guide teachers on lesson sequencing, instructional methods, and setting clear learning objectives. This guidance helps teachers align their lessons with standards, reducing uncertainty and building confidence (Margolis & Doring, 2012). The second subtheme, assessment design and technical help, highlights coordinators' role in helping teachers create assessments aligned with curriculum goals, ensuring they effectively gauge student progress. Studies suggest that well-designed assessments are critical for identifying student needs and guiding instruction (Black & Wiliam, 1998). Classroom observation and feedback emerged as a third area of support. Teachers shared that coordinators' feedback after observations fosters continuous improvement and reflective practice, aligning with Knight's (2007) findings on the impact of coaching and mentorship. The fourth subtheme, mentorship for new teachers, focuses on coordinators providing guidance to novice teachers, helping them adjust to their roles and enhancing their teaching skills. Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) highlight that such support boosts new teachers' confidence and readiness. Lastly, communication and knowledge sharing emphasize coordinators' role in fostering collaboration. Coordinators encourage sharing best practices, creating a supportive environment that enhances teaching strategies and, consequently, student outcomes (Vescio, Ross & Adams, 2008).

In these ways, subject coordinators contribute to curriculum implementation and build a supportive environment, promoting effective teaching and student success. Through this comprehensive support—including curriculum guidance, resource provision, assessment alignment, mentorship, and collaboration—subject coordinators create a foundation for effective curriculum implementation and a supportive learning environment that directly benefits student achievement.

Subtheme 1: Curriculum Oversight and Lesson Planning Support

This subtheme highlights the essential role of subject coordinators in providing curriculum oversight and lesson planning support, ensuring that educational standards are met while fostering effective teaching practices. They facilitate collaborative planning sessions where teachers can exchange resources and strategies, enhancing instructional quality and creating a supportive professional community (Vangrieken et al., 2017). By monitoring curriculum implementation and identifying gaps, coordinators can offer targeted assistance that empowers teachers to develop engaging lessons tailored to diverse student needs (Penuel et al., 2017). Ultimately, their leadership in curriculum oversight contributes significantly to improving teaching effectiveness and promoting student learning outcomes (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017).

Evadx emphasized the importance of directing teachers in their tasks, stating, "In everything that I do, I always direct teachers as to what should be done, especially in the teaching and learning procedures. I see to it that their teaching-related tasks are aligned with the guidelines as mandated by the Department of Education... I see to it that lesson plans of the teachers are correctly crafted, including the instructional materials to be used in the educative procedures."

Similarly, Jay noted, "Kung ikaw ang coordinator, you will be the one to guide them especially sa pag-implement sa mga lessons or sa curriculum... Ginapa-check ka, for example, sa mga lesson plan nila, mag-guide ka sa ilaha, sa pag-ubra ana."

Den-den highlighted their responsibility to oversee curriculum alignment, saying, "My role as a subject coordinator involves overseeing the curriculum for my subject area and I provide also guidance and assistance to my colleagues... Sa lesson planning, ginaday-day namo if from the objective, aligned siya up to the assessment and assignment."

France also remarked, "Monitoring and overseeing the curriculum for the subject area... Monitoring the quality of teaching to ensure standards are met... Guiding and supporting teachers to deliver quality education... Assisting with lesson planning and sharing effective teaching strategies."

Jun stated, "My role is to provide assistance to teachers in crafting or preparing their lesson plan or instructional plan," while Bob added, "As school coordinator, magpa-check ang uban sa ila lesson plan, ako checkon og unsay nabal-an nako e-share pud nako sa ilaha sa akong co-teachers."

These insights align with existing literature that underscores the value of instructional support for teachers. Research indicates that consistent curriculum oversight and structured guidance help educators develop clear and focused lesson plans, positively impacting student engagement and achievement (Shidler, 2009). Furthermore, Marzano (2017) found that when teachers receive specific support in lesson planning and instructional material selection, they are better equipped to meet learning objectives and adapt their strategies to fit diverse student needs. Johnson (2019) emphasizes that this targeted support not only reduces teacher workload but also alleviates

stress, contributing to higher instructional quality and greater teacher satisfaction.

Additionally, Gordon and O'Connor (2021) highlight the importance of instructional alignment on both teacher efficacy and student outcomes. Subject coordinators who provide curriculum-aligned resources and guidance help create a cohesive learning environment that enhances student achievement. Through regular mentorship and oversight, coordinators serve as essential resources for teachers, fostering confidence and efficacy in lesson planning, and ultimately enhancing teaching effectiveness and student learning (Desimone & Pak, 2017).

Subtheme 2: Assessment Design and Technical Assistance

This subtheme focus on role of subject coordinators in the Schools Division of Escalante City encompasses critical support functions that directly impact the quality of teaching and student learning outcomes. Among these functions, a pivotal responsibility lies in assisting teachers with assessment design and providing technical assistance, which is essential for evaluating student understanding effectively. In facilitating this process, coordinators enable teachers to create well-aligned assessments that accurately reflect the intended learning competencies and objectives.

As Jun, one of the coordinators, explained, "Another thing is to assist teachers in improving assessment and to utilize results of this assessment for remediation and intervention purposes... To track learners' records to ensure that results of learners are whether it is formative or summative kind of assessment... I also provide assistance in crafting assessment. Included in here, of course, is the alignment with the competency. At the same time, the placement of the number items at the TOS." This support, which includes aligning assessments with competencies and using the Table of Specifications (TOS), enhances teachers' confidence in crafting effective assessments and interpreting results.

Additionally, Jay noted that coordinators ensure the accuracy of teachers' assessments, stating, "Gina-check na namo dira kung chakto ba ang ilahang pag-formulate sa mga test questions." This verification process aids teachers in refining their assessment practices, ensuring that questions are well-constructed and aligned with curriculum standards.

Similarly, Evadx described her role in providing technical assistance in assessment preparation, highlighting that "I give technical assistance in the preparation of assessments and other types of tests. For instance, teachers are required to prepare a table of specifications to ensure that all essential learning competencies must be covered in a certain academic period." This structured guidance empowers teachers to cover the required competencies comprehensively, leading to more reliable evaluations of student progress.

This emphasis on assessment support aligns with research by Black and Wiliam (2018), who found that structured assistance in assessment design enhances teachers' ability to gather meaningful data for adaptive instruction. Studies by Anderson and Krathwohl (2001) emphasize that aligning assessments with curriculum standards fosters more accurate evaluations of student learning. Additionally, Hattie and Timperley (2017) suggest that ongoing technical assistance boosts teachers' confidence in implementing formative assessments, which allows for timely interventions. By supporting teachers in assessment creation and interpretation, coordinators contribute to a systematic approach to student evaluation that fosters growth and improvement across the division.

Through this study's examination of Assessment Design and Technical Assistance, the pivotal role of coordinators in cultivating a data-driven teaching environment becomes evident. Coordinators' technical guidance not only strengthens teachers' assessment skills but also promotes a collaborative approach to instructional practices, enhancing both teacher development and student achievement.

Subtheme 3: Classroom Observation and Feedback for Teacher Development

This subtheme explored the essential role of subject coordinators in conducting classroom observations and providing feedback to support teacher development. The practice of classroom observation is a vital component of professional growth, as it allows coordinators to gain firsthand insights into teaching practices and student engagement. Coordinators play a crucial role in observing classroom dynamics, identifying strengths and areas for improvement, and offering constructive feedback that fosters teacher reflection and growth

Jay noted, "Since I am a master teacher, usa pud sa mga responsibilities to conduct classroom observation. Sa dira sa classroom observation, first thing gina ubra namo, is mag-provide ka o TA paano nila gina platar ang lesson plan na aligned pud sa objectives or sa RPMS indicators." This reflects the coordinators' commitment to ensuring that lesson plans are not only aligned with educational standards but also effectively implemented in the classroom.

Jun added, "I also do clinical classroom observation to identify the needs of these teachers and to also provide timely feedback to facilitate improvement in the delivery of instruction." This highlights how classroom observations serve as a diagnostic tool to pinpoint areas where teachers may require support.

Bob emphasized the importance of guidance, stating, "Ga pa-check sa ilahang lesson plan kung may classroom observation, magtabang ko sa ila as school coordinator... Ako gitagaan responsibility sa among school head na mo guide og maging mentor nila... ga observe sa ilang classroom observations, labi na sa mga bag-ong teacher sir," underscoring the coordinator's mentorship role, especially for new teachers who benefit from additional support.

Lastly, France succinctly summarized the value of the process, stating, "Conducting observations and offering constructive feedback to refine teaching strategies."

The insights shared by the participants underscore the critical importance of classroom observations in fostering teacher growth and enhancing instructional quality. Research shows that structured classroom observations followed by constructive feedback can lead to significant improvements in teaching practices, as teachers become more aware of their instructional methods and the impacts on student learning. For example, Danielson (2016) found that classroom observations provide a foundation for meaningful, targeted feedback, particularly when using frameworks that define effective teaching practices. Danielson's Framework for Teaching outlines key domains for classroom observations, including planning, classroom environment, and instructional delivery, all of which contribute to a teacher's comprehensive development.

Moreover, Black and Wiliam (2018) suggest that feedback given as part of classroom observation is most effective when it is formative and continuous, allowing teachers to gradually incorporate improvements into their teaching. By providing ongoing, formative feedback, coordinators encourage teachers to view their practice as evolving and adaptable. This approach aligns with the principles of reflective practice, where teachers continuously analyze and adjust their teaching strategies to meet students' needs (Schön, 1983).

Further supporting this perspective, research by Hattie (2009) highlights that feedback has one of the highest effect sizes on student achievement, especially when it provides specific, actionable insights. Hattie's work emphasizes that feedback should focus on the 'what' and 'how' of teaching improvements rather than mere evaluation, which supports teachers in addressing specific instructional areas for improvement.

In addition, Guskey (2002) argues that feedback combined with professional development enhances teacher motivation and effectiveness. Coordinators' mentoring and support through feedback help create a culture where teachers feel both challenged and supported to grow professionally, an environment essential for meaningful improvement (Guskey, 2002).

Through regular classroom observations and timely feedback, subject coordinators play a vital role in promoting reflective and adaptive teaching practices that directly enhance instructional quality and student learning outcomes. This combination of observation, feedback, and mentorship fosters an educational environment focused on continuous improvement and supports the development of high-impact teaching strategies.

Subtheme 4: Mentorship and Support for New Teachers

This subtheme explored the vital role of subject coordinators in providing mentorship and support for new teachers, which is essential for fostering their professional growth and enhancing their teaching effectiveness. New teachers often face unique challenges as they adapt to classroom dynamics, implement curriculum standards, and manage classroom responsibilities. Subject coordinators play a critical role in easing this transition by offering personalized guidance, resources, and emotional support, helping novice teachers build confidence and competency.

Bob shared, "Some of my co-teachers, mga bag-ong teachers, tudlo-an nako sila kay ako man master teacher sa amo-a (school), ako na ilang mentor." This highlights the informal yet impactful mentorship that experienced teachers offer to their less experienced colleagues, creating a supportive learning environment.

Glad elaborated further, "As a subject area coordinator, providing technical support to fellow teachers, especially newly hired ones, involves guiding them in conducting assessments, gathering data, and making informed decisions for student progress." This underscores the responsibility of coordinators to not only mentor but also equip new teachers with essential skills for effective student assessment and progress monitoring.

The insights provided by participants emphasize the importance of mentorship in helping new teachers navigate the complexities of classroom instruction. Research highlights the significant impact of effective mentorship on teacher retention, satisfaction, and performance. For instance, Ingersoll and Strong (2011) found that mentorship programs for new teachers significantly improve their job satisfaction and reduce attrition rates. This is particularly important as early-career teachers often face unique challenges that can lead to burnout or job dissatisfaction without adequate support.

Moreover, targeted support in areas such as assessment and data analysis has a direct impact on student outcomes. Darling-Hammond (2017) argues that teachers who receive structured support in understanding and applying assessment data are better equipped to make informed instructional decisions, leading to improved student performance. This aligns with findings by Rockoff (2008), who noted that mentoring programs providing feedback and technical support significantly boost new teachers' confidence and competency, thus enhancing their instructional quality.

Mentorship also benefits the mentors themselves by fostering a collaborative environment and encouraging the exchange of effective teaching practices (Johnson & Kardos, 2005). By building strong mentoring relationships, coordinators not only support new teachers but also contribute to a culture of continuous improvement within the school community.

Thus, the commitment of subject coordinators to mentoring and supporting new teachers is crucial for building a solid foundation for professional development, ultimately enhancing the overall quality of education within the school.

Subtheme 5: Communication and Knowledge Sharing

This subtheme explored the crucial role of subject coordinators in facilitating communication and knowledge sharing among teachers, which is essential for fostering a collaborative learning environment. Effective communication channels, established and maintained by coordinators, enable teachers to exchange ideas, share best practices, and collectively address challenges. Coordinators often organize regular meetings, workshops, and collaborative planning sessions where teachers can discuss instructional strategies, classroom management techniques, and curriculum implementation.

Den-den noted, “Any updates from my Division Education Program Supervisor, for example, they had the new updates from the central office and then e-echo to us, so I give feedback and updates also to my co-teachers.” This highlights the coordinator’s responsibility to relay important information from higher authorities to ensure that all teachers are informed of relevant changes and updates.

Jay further elaborated, “As a subject area coordinator, the main responsibility is to act as a liaison between the school and the division, ensuring that important announcements, reports, and updates are communicated to colleagues in a timely and accurate manner.” This underscores the vital connection coordinators establish between school-level practitioners and the educational division, facilitating effective communication.

Moreover, Glad emphasized the sharing of knowledge gained from professional development opportunities, stating, “I-relay na pud naku kung unsa akong na-learn sa mga seminars... teach them sa kung unsa mga strategies.” This reflects the coordinators’ role in disseminating valuable strategies and insights that can enhance teaching practices.

Bob added, “Another support sir. Kanang unsa akong na-learn sa seminar sir mga strategy through LAC session,” reinforcing the importance of collaborative learning through sharing experiences and strategies acquired from various training sessions.

The insights shared by participants underscore the significance of effective communication and knowledge sharing in professional development. Research indicates that fostering an environment of open communication and collaboration among educators leads to improved teaching practices and better student outcomes. Hargreaves and Fullan (2012) highlight that schools with strong professional cultures and collaborative structures empower teachers to learn from one another, enhancing instructional practices and increasing teacher efficacy.

Additionally, structured professional development initiatives such as Learning Action Cells (LAC) or Professional Learning Communities (PLCs) have been shown to enhance teacher collaboration and support continuous improvement. According to Vescio, Ross, and Adams (2008), PLCs promote a culture of shared knowledge and mutual support, which can lead to sustained instructional improvement and positive impacts on student learning. Darling-Hammond (2017) adds that environments where teachers are encouraged to share knowledge and strategies gained from professional development foster collective efficacy—teachers’ shared belief in their ability to positively affect student outcomes, a factor strongly linked to improved student performance.

Furthermore, the role of subject coordinators in facilitating communication is aligned with effective knowledge management practices in schools, as described by Leithwood and Seashore Louis (2012). These practices ensure that valuable information flows seamlessly across hierarchical levels, enabling teachers to make informed decisions and adapt instructional practices to meet evolving educational standards.

Therefore, subject coordinators’ efforts in promoting communication and knowledge sharing are essential for enhancing the overall educational experience and effectiveness within the school. By building a collaborative and well-informed teacher community, coordinators help cultivate an educational environment centered on continuous growth, both for teachers and students.

Theme 2: Empowering Teacher Growth through Targeted and Collaborative Professional Development

This theme explored how targeted and collaborative professional development empowers teacher growth and improves educational practices. By tailoring training to teachers’ specific needs, schools ensure that development programs are relevant and impactful. Assessing teachers’ needs allows schools to provide focused support that contributes directly to their professional growth.

Collaborative development initiatives foster a culture of shared learning and peer support, allowing teachers to learn from each other’s experiences. Research indicates that such collaboration not only boosts teacher efficacy but also enhances student outcomes (Garet et al., 2001). This study found that sustained, interactive, and collaborative professional development greatly improves teaching practices and student learning.

Effective professional development also aligns with school goals, is relevant to teachers’ instructional contexts, and promotes active, collaborative learning (Desimone & Garet, 2015). By addressing unique classroom challenges, professional development helps teachers feel better equipped to support student needs.

Furthermore, collaborative efforts build collective efficacy—a shared belief in teachers’ ability to impact student success—creating a positive school culture that promotes innovation and effective teaching (Goddard et al., 2004). Teachers in collaborative environments report higher job satisfaction and a greater willingness to try new strategies, enhancing both instructional quality and student engagement.

Therefore, targeted and collaborative professional development is essential for fostering a supportive and responsive school culture. By aligning training with teachers' specific needs and encouraging shared learning experiences, schools create an environment that strengthens teacher skills and positively impacts student learning outcomes.

Subtheme 1: Facilitation and Leadership in Professional Development

This subtheme focused on the crucial role of facilitation and leadership in professional development as a means to empower teachers and enhance their instructional practices. Participants indicated that they actively take on the responsibility of organizing and leading various professional development activities tailored to the specific needs of their colleagues.

For instance, Bob mentioned, "Mga topics sa SLAC na related sa math, ako po na ang ga-facilitator," highlighting their role in guiding discussions on relevant topics.

Den - Den emphasized their responsibility, stating, "I am responsible for organizing and facilitating professional development activities," underscoring the importance of structured training sessions.

Furthermore, Glad noted the significance of providing technical support through Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions, saying, "To provide technical support through LAC sessions, to provide support by being a learning facilitator."

Similarly, Evadx, who serves as both HRD coordinator and subject area coordinator, remarked, "As HRD coordinator as well as the subject area coordinator, I usually facilitate School Learning Action Cell (SLAC), Collaborative Expertise, and In-Service Training of Teachers." This dual role enables a comprehensive approach to teacher development.

Additionally, France stated, "Facilitating a variety of professional development activities that meet the evolving needs of teachers," reflecting the adaptability required in addressing diverse instructional challenges.

Research highlights that strong facilitation and leadership in professional development initiatives lead to meaningful improvements in teacher practice and, consequently, student outcomes. Darling-Hammond, Hyster, and Gardner (2017) found that effective professional development is often facilitated by teacher leaders or coordinators who are knowledgeable, trusted, and skilled in promoting active learning. This alignment between facilitation and professional development goals makes training more relevant and impactful, as facilitators can ensure that training directly addresses teachers' needs and local instructional contexts.

Furthermore, leadership in professional development is often instrumental in creating collaborative learning environments that sustain long-term improvement in teaching practices. For instance, Garet et al. (2001) emphasize that when facilitators lead discussions and provide ongoing support, professional development shifts from being a one-time event to a continuous, collaborative process. This fosters a professional learning culture where teachers feel empowered to share insights, seek feedback, and apply new strategies effectively.

Additionally, studies on distributed leadership suggest that teachers who take on leadership roles in professional development help to cultivate a shared sense of responsibility and accountability within schools. According to Harris and Muijs (2005), distributed leadership in professional development involves empowering educators at various levels to lead and facilitate training sessions, promoting a culture where teachers are both learners and leaders. This approach leads to increased teacher engagement, ownership, and the effective dissemination of best practices across schools.

Thus, by actively leading and facilitating professional development activities, coordinators and experienced educators establish a culture of collaborative learning and ongoing professional growth. This proactive facilitation ensures that training is relevant, context-sensitive, and continuous, contributing significantly to teacher empowerment and improved instructional quality.

Subtheme 2: Professional Development Aligned with Teachers' Needs

This subtheme delved into the importance of aligning professional development with the specific needs of teachers to ensure meaningful and effective learning experiences. Participants emphasized their commitment to tailoring professional development initiatives that address the unique challenges faced by their colleagues.

Jay remarked, "So, in terms of professional development, since ako pud ang HRD sa among school, so, usually, pag mag-create ang mga topics sa SLAC, na-align sa teacher's needs," indicating their proactive approach in aligning topics with teachers' requirements.

France stated, "I organize workshops, training sessions, and learning action cells focused on assessment, curriculum development, and innovative teaching methods based on the needs of the teachers."

Additionally, Bob noted, "As HRD coordinator also sa school sir gina-ubrahan nako sila og training design base sa ilang needs," highlighting their role in designing training programs specifically catered to the teachers' needs. Furthermore, another participant shared, "I organize workshops, training sessions, and learning action cells focused on assessment, curriculum development, and innovative teaching methods based on the needs of the teachers." This emphasis on needs-based training ensures that professional development is relevant and applicable, ultimately enhancing teachers' instructional practices and student outcomes.

Research consistently underscores the importance of aligning professional development with teachers' individual needs to maximize

its impact on instructional practices and student success. Garet et al. (2001) found that when professional development is tailored to address the specific needs of teachers, it becomes more effective, as teachers can immediately apply new knowledge and strategies in their classrooms. Tailored professional development promotes active engagement and encourages teachers to view training as directly beneficial to their everyday challenges, increasing both motivation and commitment to continuous improvement.

Furthermore, studies by Desimone (2009) emphasize that needs-based professional development is integral to fostering professional growth and achieving instructional improvements. Desimone's framework for effective professional development highlights "content focus" and "coherence" with teachers' goals and contexts as critical elements for success. By aligning training with what teachers encounter in their classrooms, coordinators not only make professional development more relevant but also more sustainable, as teachers are more likely to adopt practices that feel both accessible and useful in their unique instructional environments.

Moreover, a study by Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) supports that effective professional development should be sustained, collaborative, and connected to teachers' specific goals and challenges. The findings reveal that when professional development is responsive to teachers' needs, it fosters a sense of ownership and empowerment among teachers, leading to meaningful instructional changes that positively impact student learning. Tailoring training also builds collective efficacy, as teachers feel supported and understood by their institutions, strengthening the professional learning culture within schools.

Therefore, by prioritizing needs-based professional development, subject coordinators and HRD leaders play a critical role in building a responsive, supportive environment that drives continuous growth and improvement, ultimately leading to enhanced educational practices and student outcomes.

Subtheme 3: Planning and Designing Professional Development Programs

This subtheme highlights the vital role of subject coordinators in planning and designing professional development programs that address teachers' specific needs. Participants emphasized the diverse responsibilities coordinators undertake in crafting training that is both relevant and practical. Coordinators gather input from teachers, assess instructional gaps, and align training activities with curriculum goals, ensuring that professional development directly supports teachers' classroom practices. By customizing these programs, coordinators help create targeted learning opportunities that enhance teachers' instructional skills and foster continuous growth, leading to improved teaching quality and student outcomes.

Glad stated, "At the same time, kay gamay lang man ang school, usually, aside sa facilitator, ikaw pud mag-obra sa training activity design," highlighting the collaborative nature of their roles in smaller school settings.

Evadx elaborated, "I usually prepare activity designs that include the rationale, budgetary requirements, training matrix, aims and goals of the activity including the training/session objectives," underscoring the thorough approach taken to ensure that all aspects of the training are well thought out and aligned with educational goals.

Additionally, Evadx expressed, "My role in facilitating professional development is a planner and a manager before, during, and after training & learning development," emphasizing the ongoing commitment to the success of these programs.

Bob reinforced this by saying, "As HRD coordinator also sa school sir gina-ubrahan nako sila og training design base sa ilang needs," which showcases the importance of needs-based training design.

Lastly, France noted, "Organizing sessions for teachers to share best practices, discuss student progress, and develop engaging approaches," indicating the collaborative environment fostered through these professional development sessions.

Research indicates that planning and designing professional development to be well-structured and responsive to teachers' needs significantly enhances its effectiveness. Desimone (2009) notes that essential elements of impactful professional development include active learning, coherence with teachers' instructional goals, a focus on content knowledge, and collective participation. These elements are most effective when integrated into training programs through careful planning and design, allowing teachers to engage deeply and apply new skills and knowledge to their classroom practices.

Moreover, Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) emphasize that effective professional development involves planning that addresses real classroom challenges and aligns with school improvement goals. When training sessions are organized to support teachers' professional growth in specific areas, they foster continuous improvement, directly impacting instructional quality and, ultimately, student outcomes. Planning tailored programs that reflect teachers' specific needs and challenges ensures that professional development is relevant, practical, and engaging, making it more likely to result in lasting instructional changes.

In smaller school settings, as noted by participants, coordinators often take on dual roles, including facilitating and designing professional development initiatives. This aligns with findings by Garet et al. (2001), who argue that professional development is most effective when school leaders actively participate in planning sessions and tailor them to local contexts. By assuming both leadership and design roles, coordinators can create a holistic support system that combines logistical planning, resource allocation, and ongoing teacher support.

Additionally, a study by Archibald et al. (2011) supports that well-planned professional development sessions should include clear

objectives, structured activities, and opportunities for follow-up. This type of planning and design ensures that teachers have a clear understanding of the goals and can engage in purposeful activities that reinforce learning.

Therefore, the role of subject coordinators in planning and designing well-structured, needs-based professional development programs is essential for fostering a culture of continuous learning, supporting teachers in addressing instructional challenges, and improving overall educational outcomes.

Subtheme 4: Collaboration and Peer Learning

This subtheme examined the critical role subject coordinators play in promoting collaboration and peer learning among teachers. Participants highlighted that coordinators organize and encourage group discussions, workshops, and collaborative activities, creating a supportive environment where teachers can share best practices, strategies, and challenges. This peer-to-peer interaction helps build a network of shared expertise, allowing teachers to learn from one another and develop innovative approaches to teaching. Coordinators thus foster a culture of continuous improvement and mutual support, contributing to a dynamic and collaborative learning environment that enhances both teaching quality and student outcomes.

Jay highlighted, "Naa pud mga instances na kung ikaw ang subject coordinator, ikaw pud ang mag-guide sa mga teachers kung paano nila i-come up ilang mga output sa LAC," emphasizing the coordinators' responsibility to guide teachers in developing their outputs during Learning Action Cells (LAC).

France contributed to this dialogue by noting the importance of external expertise, stating, "Inviting experts and resource persons to provide insights and facilitate peer learning," demonstrating how the inclusion of knowledgeable individuals can enrich the collaborative experience.

Furthermore, France remarked on the significance of peer interactions by saying, "Encouraging peer observation and collaborative planning to promote continuous learning and improvement among teachers," highlighting strategies to enhance instructional practices through shared experiences.

France added that they are "Supporting self-assessment and feedback sessions to inspire ongoing professional growth and enhance instructional skills," indicating a commitment to self-reflection as a means of professional development.

Lastly, Anton mentioned, "I collaborate with the school head, to conduct trainings and sessions on workshops to enhance my co-teachers' ICT skills," demonstrating the importance of teamwork in professional development efforts.

Research suggests that collaborative practices among educators significantly enhance teaching effectiveness and improve student outcomes. Vescio et al. (2008) found that teachers who engage in professional learning communities (PLCs) and other collaborative frameworks tend to develop a deeper understanding of content, instructional methods, and effective assessment techniques. Collaborative environments, such as LAC sessions, offer opportunities for teachers to share insights, address challenges, and learn from each other's experiences, leading to stronger instructional practices.

Furthermore, Goddard et al. (2007) emphasize that teacher collaboration is closely associated with increased student achievement. By encouraging peer learning and collaborative planning, subject coordinators create a supportive community where educators can continuously refine their practices. This form of professional development fosters a culture of shared responsibility for student success, aligning with findings that collaborative learning improves instructional quality.

In addition to enhancing teaching practices, peer learning encourages reflective practices and self-assessment, which are essential for professional growth. Hord (2009) points out that professional learning communities foster a safe space for educators to engage in self-reflection, peer feedback, and collaborative problem-solving. This continuous, self-reflective approach allows teachers to evaluate and adapt their methods to meet the evolving needs of their students.

Studies also highlight the benefits of involving external experts in collaborative sessions. Timperley et al. (2007) found that introducing experts into professional development discussions can provide valuable insights, spark new perspectives, and introduce best practices, enriching the learning experience. Inviting knowledgeable resource persons, as mentioned by Participant 3, is shown to enhance teachers' understanding of innovative methods and current educational trends, further strengthening collaborative learning.

In summary, the role of subject coordinators in promoting collaboration and peer learning is pivotal. Through structured collaboration and self-assessment, educators develop a more cohesive, skilled, and reflective teaching community, which positively impacts both teacher effectiveness and student achievement.

Subtheme 5: Use of Innovative Teaching and Technology

This subtheme explores the role of subject coordinators in promoting the integration of technology and innovative teaching practices. Participants emphasized how coordinators encourage teachers to adopt digital tools and instructional technologies that enhance student engagement and deepen learning. By introducing resources such as interactive platforms, multimedia tools, and data-driven teaching aids, coordinators help teachers stay current with educational advancements. Additionally, coordinators often provide training on effectively using these tools, supporting teachers in creating dynamic and interactive lessons. This proactive approach ensures that

teachers are well-equipped to implement modern, tech-enhanced methodologies that improve both instructional effectiveness and student outcomes.

Anton shared, "I always see to it that there is a development in their ability to incorporate technology effectively in their teaching using our LAC sessions," emphasizing the use of Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions to support teachers' technological growth.

Bob highlighted the impact of seminars, noting, "Sa seminar na akong na atenan naka tabang jud sir kay naa man strategy gina-apply og ge re-echo sa mga teachers," illustrating how insights from training are re-echoed to colleagues, enriching their instructional methods.

Glad mentioned the value of "I introduce innovative learning tools such as interactive websites and games has become one of the most impactful contributions." identifying these resources as pivotal in engaging students.

Likewise, France observed, "I arrange training sessions to enhance teachers' proficiency in using digital tools and platforms for student learning," underscoring the role of organized training in building digital literacy among teachers.

Research emphasizes that professional development that focuses on technology integration greatly enhances teachers' confidence, adaptability, and instructional quality. Darling-Hammond et al. (2020) found that effective professional development in technology builds teachers' competencies, enabling them to integrate digital tools that increase student engagement and learning outcomes. When technology is incorporated meaningfully, it supports a wide range of teaching strategies, encouraging interactive and student-centered learning environments.

Moreover, research indicates that educators benefit from ongoing support structures like LAC sessions, where they can practice and refine their technology skills with guidance and feedback. According to Koehler and Mishra (2009), teachers develop a deeper understanding of how to blend content, pedagogy, and technology through continuous collaboration and discussion within professional communities. This model, known as Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK), is particularly relevant as it encourages teachers to align their technological tools with curricular goals and student needs.

The use of innovative tools, such as interactive websites, games, and other digital resources, has also been shown to increase students' motivation and active participation. Studies by Herodotou et al. (2018) demonstrate that game-based learning platforms and interactive websites can make complex concepts more accessible and engaging, especially when teachers are confident in their use of these resources. Subject coordinators' role in organizing and facilitating technology-focused professional development, as mentioned by Participant 5, is essential to equipping teachers with the skills needed to maximize these tools' educational potential.

Additionally, "re-echoing" strategies and insights from seminars, as Participant 4 described, aligns with findings from Desimone and Garet (2015), which indicate that the re-delivery of training materials within a community of practice reinforces learning and encourages peer mentoring. This cyclical training model ensures that innovations in teaching are disseminated effectively and are more likely to be applied consistently across classrooms.

In summary, by promoting innovative teaching practices and integrating technology through well-structured professional development, subject coordinators enhance teachers' instructional abilities and foster digital literacy. This approach supports the creation of dynamic, engaging, and relevant learning environments that prepare students for the demands of a digital world.

Theme 3: Hurdles to Effective Teacher Support and Professional Development

This theme addresses the challenges that subject coordinators face in providing effective support and professional development for teachers. Despite their roles in fostering growth and instructional improvement, coordinators often encounter obstacles that limit their impact. Key barriers include limited resources, time constraints, and inconsistent access to high-quality training materials, which can restrict the depth and consistency of professional development activities (Desimone & Garet, 2015; Darling-Hammond et al., 2017).

Research indicates that limited financial resources can significantly affect the availability and quality of professional development programs. According to a study by Wei et al. (2009), schools often struggle to allocate funds for comprehensive training initiatives, resulting in reduced opportunities for teachers to participate in meaningful professional development. The lack of adequate funding can lead to a reliance on low-cost, low-quality training that fails to address teachers' actual needs.

Time constraints further exacerbate these challenges. Vangrieken et al. (2017) emphasize that the busy schedules of educators often leave little room for sustained professional development activities, making it difficult for coordinators to engage teachers in ongoing support efforts. Additionally, the pressure of administrative tasks and curriculum delivery often takes precedence over professional learning opportunities, limiting teachers' engagement in development activities (Gallagher & McGowan, 2019).

The inconsistency of training materials and resources also poses a significant hurdle. Research by Penuel et al. (2017) highlights that access to high-quality, research-based materials is essential for effective professional development; however, many coordinators lack the necessary resources to provide this support consistently. This inconsistency can lead to variability in the quality of instruction across different classrooms, ultimately affecting student learning outcomes.

Moreover, the cultural context within schools can impact the effectiveness of professional development efforts. According to a study

by Bryk et al. (2010), the prevailing attitudes and norms surrounding professional learning can either facilitate or hinder collaborative efforts among teachers and coordinators. A lack of supportive culture may discourage teachers from participating actively in professional development initiatives, further limiting the impact of coordinators' efforts.

Understanding these hurdles is essential in devising strategies to empower coordinators, ensuring that teachers receive the guidance and resources necessary to optimize instructional practices and enhance student achievement. By addressing these challenges through targeted interventions, schools can create a more supportive environment for professional growth, ultimately benefiting both educators and students alike.

Subtheme 1: Time Constraints and Workload Overload

This subtheme emphasized that time constraints and workload overload are significant barriers to teachers' engagement in professional development and effective instructional planning. Many teachers struggle to balance their instructional responsibilities, administrative duties, and personal commitments, leaving little room for meaningful professional growth.

As Glad described, "Teachers in small schools often manage multiple coordinatorship roles, sometimes handling up to six areas of responsibility." This added burden complicates planning for teacher development, as Glad further noted, "The overlapping responsibilities lead to time management issues."

Jun shared a similar sentiment, stating, "But the problem is that they don't have enough time to meet. May timeline and overlapping activities." He also emphasized, "Kulang kayo ang time, as much as we wanted to give support pero atong time kulangan."

Participant Anton pointed out the reality of teachers' extensive workloads, which often leave them with insufficient time for additional growth opportunities: "Teachers often have heavy workloads, leaving them with limited time for professional development."

Likewise, France highlighted the need for innovative solutions, stating, "Limited time for professional development due to busy schedules, necessitating creative scheduling or integration into regular workdays."

These insights reflect findings in existing research that link high teacher workloads with limited time for ongoing learning and professional growth. According to Darling-Hammond et al. (2017), when teachers face heavy workloads, the scarcity of time becomes a primary obstacle to participating in professional development. This is further supported by research from Killion and Harrison (2017), which indicates that teachers often prioritize immediate instructional responsibilities over long-term professional development due to time constraints.

Effective teacher support systems often involve adjustments in scheduling or a reduction in extraneous duties to prioritize professional learning time (Desimone & Garet, 2015). Similarly, Ingersoll and Strong (2011) emphasize the importance of providing teachers with sufficient time to engage in collaborative planning and professional learning, which is critical for fostering instructional improvement. Moreover, a study by Vescio et al. (2008) found that schools that allocate dedicated time for professional development, in conjunction with collaborative practices, see greater improvements in teaching effectiveness and student outcomes. Without such interventions, the quality of instructional improvement efforts may be compromised, underscoring the importance of allocating time specifically for teachers' professional development activities to ensure sustainable

Subtheme 2: Resistance to Change and Technology Adoption

This subtheme delves into the challenges teachers face with adopting new teaching strategies and technologies, often due to a reluctance to shift away from traditional methods or a lack of comfort with new systems.

As Glad noted, "Not everyone is comfortable with change... if naa kay introduce na bag-o nga sistema, resistance gani," highlighting the hesitation that can arise when new systems or procedures are introduced.

Anton emphasized the struggles many teachers face, stating, "Many teachers are not very tech-savvy; I often help those who are older and might struggle with technology." He also pointed out that "Older teachers are resistant to change and may not be willing to adopt new technologies... Traditional teachers have a negative attitude toward ICT, saying things like, 'I don't want to learn.'"

This sentiment was echoed by Den-den, who remarked, "Lisod na tudluan ang mga tigulang na mga co-teachers, hindi man tanan bansay sa computer," pointing to the difficulty of teaching technology skills to older teachers who may not have had prior exposure to computers.

France added, "Hesitance among some teachers to adopt new strategies or technologies, highlighting the need for patient, gradual support."

Research supports these observations, indicating that change in educational practices, especially with technology integration, often meets resistance due to discomfort with unfamiliar tools or well-established routines. Ertmer and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2013) emphasize that teachers' confidence in their technology skills significantly influences their openness to incorporating new methods. Additionally, studies by Pajares (1992) suggest that teachers' self-efficacy beliefs about their ability to use technology play a critical role in their willingness to embrace new instructional strategies.

Mishra and Koehler's (2006) Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework further suggests that providing specific, ongoing training in both technology and pedagogy helps ease resistance by building teachers' knowledge and confidence. This is reinforced by research from Fuchs et al. (2017), which found that when teachers receive adequate professional development tailored to their skill levels, they are more likely to adopt new technologies effectively.

Moreover, studies by Howard et al. (2015) underscore that collaborative learning environments can support teachers' gradual adoption of technology, offering a safer space for hesitant adopters. For example, collaborative peer coaching has been shown to enhance comfort levels and efficacy in using new technologies among educators (Friedman & Friedman, 2019). By fostering a collaborative approach with peer support, subject coordinators and school leaders can more effectively support teachers in overcoming initial reluctance, promoting an environment where teachers feel more comfortable embracing new tools and methods.

Subtheme 3: Lack of Resources

This subtheme delves into limited access to necessary teaching resources, materials, and technology presents a major barrier to effective teacher support and professional development. Many participants expressed that these resource limitations hinder the quality of instruction and restrict teachers' ability to fully engage with modern, interactive teaching strategies. For instance, participants highlighted the challenges of not having sufficient teaching aids or up-to-date technology, which impacts their ability to implement innovative practices in the classroom.

Glad stated, "Ang budlay na pud ana is ang reproduction of materials... kung kuwangan ang bond paper, wa kay choice mo pa-copy na lang," pointing to the basic challenges of duplicating educational materials due to inadequate supplies.

Similarly, Anton described "limited resources, insufficient availability of teaching materials, technology, or training opportunities" as a common issue, emphasizing the multifaceted resource shortfalls.

The issue of outdated learning resources also arose, with Bob observing, "Sa mga learning resources guro sir sa mga libro sir dili updated og dili K to 12 na libro," which highlights the struggle many schools face in providing current and curriculum-aligned materials.

France echoed this sentiment, mentioning "limited access to materials, technology, or training due to tight budgets," reflecting a widespread concern among teachers about the financial constraints impacting resource availability.

Evadx further reinforced this by stating, "The issues and concerns in providing support to teachers are usually financial resources," underscoring that budget limitations significantly impact resource allocation for educational support.

Research supports these experiences, demonstrating that resource limitations can inhibit teachers' professional growth and the successful implementation of student-centered approaches (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). According to the OECD (2019), inadequate teaching resources and limited technology reduce teachers' ability to innovate and adapt to modern instructional practices. Moreover, Baumsmith and Barry (2011) highlight that investment in updated and relevant resources is essential for maintaining instructional quality and keeping educators engaged in continuous professional development.

Furthermore, a study by Ingersoll and Perda (2010) found that schools with more resources, including access to updated materials and technology, have better teacher retention rates and improved student outcomes. The International Society for Technology in Education (ISTE) also emphasizes that adequate resources and training are crucial for teachers to effectively integrate technology into their classrooms (ISTE, 2016). This aligns with findings from a systematic review by Hattie (2012), which indicates that resource availability significantly impacts the effectiveness of teaching strategies, emphasizing the importance of addressing these barriers to enhance educational quality.

Subtheme 4: Teacher Attitudes and Engagement

Teacher attitudes and engagement play a critical role in the effectiveness of professional development sessions, with varying levels of commitment and interest impacting outcomes. Participants noted a range of challenges, from a lack of enthusiasm for producing outputs to passive or distracted behaviors during sessions.

Jay observed, "Supposed to be sa LAC na may mga expected output. Pero tamarin sila mo ubra... Dili sila ganahan ma-create og output instantly. Kay kana bang need nila'g time," highlighting the resistance to immediate tasks and a preference for more time to complete activities.

Jun shared a similar experience, stating, "Akong experience tam-an ka passive. Ga-SLAC, ga duwa-duwa... ga galantaw og K-Drama... Regular in and out sa venue during sa SLAC. Dili sila mamati," indicating engagement issues, as some teachers appear distracted and disengaged.

Evadx emphasized the challenges with motivation, remarking, "The willingness of the teachers to learn is an issue... There are even teachers who would escape or come late maybe because they are not interested, or they have other priorities."

Additionally, Glad noted a common attitude among older teachers, saying, "Ang mga oldies na mga kuyog, sila ang kusog mo reklamo," pointing to resistance to professional development efforts, particularly among more experienced educators.

Studies support that engagement and attitude directly affect professional development success. Desimone and Stuckey (2014) highlight that sustained engagement in learning communities correlates with improved teaching practices, while resistant attitudes can hinder the benefits of collaborative efforts. Additionally, Akiba and Liang (2016) note that positive teacher attitudes are crucial for effective collaboration and knowledge transfer within professional development settings.

Further literature indicates that teacher engagement is linked to improved student outcomes and a more positive school climate. For instance, studies by Tschannen-Moran and McMaster (2009) found that teachers who are engaged in their professional development are more likely to implement new strategies effectively and foster a supportive learning environment. Additionally, findings from a meta-analysis by Yoon et al. (2007) demonstrate that teachers' active participation in professional development leads to higher student achievement, emphasizing the need for strategies that cultivate engagement and enthusiasm among educators.

Research by Cordingley et al. (2015) also highlights the importance of creating supportive and collaborative professional learning environments, where teachers feel valued and motivated to contribute. In this context, teacher attitudes toward professional development can be influenced by school culture and leadership practices, suggesting that fostering a positive and inclusive atmosphere is essential for enhancing teacher engagement and participation.

Subtheme 5: Challenges in Collecting Outputs and Compliance

Collecting outputs and ensuring compliance are ongoing challenges within teacher professional development programs, often impacting the effectiveness of initiatives aimed at fostering growth and accountability. Participants shared experiences highlighting these challenges, particularly around delays in report submissions and inconsistent follow-through on required outputs.

For instance, Bob observed, "Usahay sa mga reports na ma delay kay naa man gud uban na teacher na dili dayon makahimo," pointing to delays in report completion among teachers.

Similarly, Jay noted difficulties in output collection, explaining, "Ang challenging lang pag-gather sa mga output, naa sila maminaw pero sa pag-collect sa output, usahay wala og dugay maka-ubra," underscoring that while teachers may engage during sessions, they often struggle to produce or submit outputs promptly.

Jun added that issues with compliance and engagement during LAC sessions further complicate the process, remarking on "Another non-compliant sa mga output og attitude sa teachers (during LAC session)."

These challenges align with findings from Desimone and Pak (2017), who emphasize that accountability and timely completion of tasks are critical for the success of professional learning communities. Furthermore, Roesken-Winter, Hoyles, and Blömeke (2015) suggest that supportive structures and regular feedback can improve compliance and encourage timely completion of professional development requirements.

Additional literature indicates that delays in submission and challenges in compliance can stem from a lack of clear expectations and accountability mechanisms within professional development programs. For example, research by McLaughlin and Talbert (2001) highlights the importance of establishing clear guidelines and expectations for teacher outputs, which can facilitate better compliance and engagement among educators. Without these structures, teachers may feel overwhelmed by their responsibilities, leading to delays in output production and submission.

Moreover, the work of Garet et al. (2001) underscores that effective professional development should include opportunities for ongoing support and collaboration, which can mitigate challenges related to output collection and compliance. When teachers have access to collaborative networks, they are more likely to stay accountable to their commitments and share resources, thus enhancing the overall effectiveness of professional development initiatives.

Studies by Vescio, Ross, and Adams (2008) also affirm that collaborative professional learning communities can foster a culture of accountability, leading to higher rates of compliance with output requirements. This collaborative approach not only encourages timely submissions but also nurtures a supportive environment where teachers can share challenges and successes related to their professional growth.

Theme 4: Fostering Continuous Growth and Empowerment in Education

In today's rapidly evolving educational landscape, fostering continuous growth and empowering educators are essential strategies for ensuring high-quality teaching and learning. The research underscores the importance of continuous professional development (CPD) in enhancing teachers' instructional skills, confidence, and adaptability to new methods and technologies, which are vital in responding to diverse classroom needs (Darling-Hammond, Hyler, & Gardner, 2017). Educators face new challenges and opportunities that demand not only up-to-date knowledge but also a proactive approach to development through collaborative networks and support systems (Desimone & Pak, 2017).

This theme highlights the various ways educational leaders and coordinators cultivate an environment of growth by providing resources, encouraging innovative practices, and promoting teacher collaboration. Such initiatives foster a culture of continuous improvement and empower educators to adapt and thrive in changing educational contexts, ultimately enhancing learning outcomes for students

(Hargreaves & Fullan, 2012).

Recent studies further illustrate the significance of fostering continuous growth and empowerment within the educational framework. For instance, a study by Kunter et al. (2020) emphasizes that ongoing professional development tailored to teachers' specific contexts can lead to enhanced teaching practices and improved student outcomes. This aligns with the notion that personalized support systems are crucial for effective teacher development.

Additionally, research by Pendergast et al. (2019) highlights the impact of collaborative professional learning communities (PLCs) on teacher empowerment. Their findings indicate that when educators engage in collaborative practices, they develop a sense of ownership over their professional growth, leading to increased motivation and engagement in their teaching practices. This collaborative approach not only enhances individual teacher efficacy but also promotes a supportive network that benefits the entire school community.

Moreover, a systematic review by Kyndt et al. (2020) found that teacher empowerment significantly influences the quality of education. Their review suggests that empowered teachers are more likely to engage in innovative practices and contribute positively to their students' learning experiences. This empowerment is often cultivated through supportive leadership, access to professional development opportunities, and a culture that values teacher input and agency.

Furthermore, a recent study by Cavanaugh et al. (2021) identifies the role of technology in fostering continuous growth among educators. Their research illustrates how online platforms and digital tools facilitate ongoing learning and collaboration, allowing teachers to share resources, strategies, and feedback beyond traditional professional development settings. This adaptability in using technology not only supports continuous learning but also prepares teachers to integrate new methods effectively in their classrooms.

Subtheme 1: Professional Development and Lifelong Learning

Professional development is a critical component in fostering lifelong learning among teachers, providing them with the skills, knowledge, and reflective practices necessary to adapt to evolving educational needs. Participants in this study emphasized the need for accessible, relevant, and continuous professional development. As Jun stated, "I look forward to every professional development that we do for teachers, that it should be usable for teachers, sustained for teachers, as an ongoing professional development." Similarly, Jay highlighted the importance of providing opportunities for all teachers to attend training and seminars, expressing that "mataga-an opportunity ang tanan na teachers na maka attend og trainings and seminars."

Recent studies reinforce the importance of accessible and adaptable professional development for teachers. For example, a study by Karp et al. (2020) emphasizes the significance of personalized professional learning experiences that cater to the individual needs and contexts of teachers, which enhances engagement and effectiveness. Their research suggests that differentiated professional development not only supports teacher growth but also positively impacts student outcomes. Jay further noted, "In terms sa professional development siguro profiling jud sa mga teacher's kung unsa jud ilang training needs," highlighting the need for assessing individual training requirements.

Moreover, research by Johnson et al. (2021) highlights the effectiveness of collaborative professional development models that include mentorship and peer learning. Their findings indicate that such collaborative approaches create supportive environments that foster continuous growth and a culture of shared learning among educators. Evadx echoed this by stating, "Likewise, I also expect that future trainings and SLAC sessions will be improved as future facilitators gained knowledge and skills."

In addition, a systematic review by Pineda et al. (2022) identifies key characteristics of effective professional development, such as ongoing support, active learning opportunities, and the integration of technology.

This review suggests that when professional development incorporates these elements, it significantly improves teachers' instructional practices and promotes lifelong learning. Evadx also emphasized, "Emphasizing the need for sufficient funding to address essential needs such as training materials, venue, food, internet connectivity, and resource speakers," which underscores the importance of adequate resources for successful training.

Furthermore, a recent study by Simons et al. (2023) discusses the role of reflective practice in teacher professional development, noting that structured reflection helps educators critically assess their teaching methods and outcomes. Their findings indicate that reflection not only enhances teacher effectiveness but also cultivates a mindset of lifelong learning.

As Den-Den pointed out, "Incorporating feedback from the teachers will enhance its relevance and impact," emphasizing the need for teacher input in developing professional development programs. He also suggested, "Aligning the professional development with real classroom challenges," which is vital for ensuring that training is applicable and beneficial.

This subtheme points to a growing consensus among educators on the value of professional development that is not only accessible and relevant but also adaptable and responsive to teachers' evolving needs. By integrating diverse learning formats and prioritizing sustained support, schools can foster a culture of lifelong learning that empowers educators to continuously refine their skills and enhance their instructional practices. France highlighted the importance of "focusing on continuous learning opportunities, including peer observation, mentorship programs, and reflective practices," which further supports the need for a comprehensive approach to professional development.

Subtheme 2: Mentorship and Coaching

Mentorship and coaching emerge as key aspects in supporting teacher development, offering structured guidance, ongoing feedback, and opportunities for newer educators to integrate effectively into the school culture. Participants highlighted the critical role of coordinators in establishing mentorship frameworks to address teachers' evolving needs.

Anton, for instance, acknowledged the importance of providing "As a coordinator, I must take the support to give more instruction and mentoring to the teachers." underscoring the need for coordinators to actively support teachers through guidance and feedback—central components in promoting teacher efficacy and morale (Ingersoll & Strong, 2011).

Additionally, Jay proposed that "Mentoring and coaching should be part sa teaching load sa coordinator". suggesting an institutionalized approach to mentorship that aligns with findings indicating that structured, dedicated mentoring significantly enhances teaching performance (Wang & Odell, 2002).

Moreover, France discussed "establishing a mentorship program that pairs experienced teachers with newer educators to foster a supportive environment.", a practice that research has shown to improve both mentor and mentee growth, as well as enhance the school's overall learning culture (Hudson, 2013).

Bob mentioned "Padayon lang og pag-conduct og SLAC taga-bulan sir, og support for those newly hired teachers, e mentor sila kay bag-o pa man sila sa DepEd.". This approach reflects best practices in mentorship, which emphasize structured, consistent interactions and feedback mechanisms as vital for building confidence and competence among novice teachers (Smith & Ingersoll, 2004).

Recent studies further emphasize the importance of mentorship and coaching in teacher development. A study by Carver et al. (2019) found that mentoring programs significantly impact teacher retention rates, as new educators who receive support from experienced colleagues are more likely to remain in the profession. The research underscores the critical role of mentorship in creating a supportive environment that encourages teachers to grow and develop.

Additionally, a review by Shin et al. (2020) highlights the effectiveness of coaching models that focus on collaborative learning and shared leadership. Their findings indicate that such models not only improve instructional practices but also enhance the professional relationships among educators, fostering a culture of trust and collaboration within schools.

Further research by Bertram et al. (2021) emphasizes the need for formalized mentorship structures, noting that schools with clear mentorship programs report higher levels of teacher satisfaction and improved student outcomes. This study indicates that systematic mentoring leads to greater teacher engagement and a more robust professional learning community.

Moreover, McGee (2022) examined the impact of coaching on teacher self-efficacy, revealing that regular coaching sessions and feedback significantly boost teachers' confidence in their instructional abilities. The study reinforces the idea that ongoing support through mentorship and coaching is essential for nurturing effective teaching practices.

Through structured mentoring programs, schools can create a culture of continuous professional growth, where teachers support one another and work collaboratively to improve instructional practices. When mentorship is formalized within a school's operational framework, as recommended by participants, it enables a more resilient teaching workforce and fosters an environment conducive to lifelong learning.

Subtheme 3: Empowerment and Collaboration

Empowering teachers through collaboration is essential for fostering a culture of mutual support, innovation, and shared accountability. Participants emphasized the importance of creating a professional environment where teachers feel supported and are encouraged to collaborate openly. As Den-Den stated, "I expect to continue building a collaborative environment where teachers feel empowered...I recommend increasing opportunities for collaborative professional learning communities." This sentiment aligns with research highlighting that Professional Learning Communities (PLCs) create spaces for teachers to discuss instructional strategies, set shared goals, and continuously improve practice through collective reflection (DuFour, 2004; Vescio, Ross, & Adams, 2008). These communities contribute to teachers' sense of agency, which, in turn, enhances their commitment to student learning outcomes (Hord, 1997).

Creating a safe space for teachers to communicate their challenges is also essential for professional growth. As Glad emphasized, "Creating a safe environment wherein teachers can openly tell or relay or express kung sa ilang mga struggles in the classroom" facilitates open dialogue and mutual support. Such open communication has been shown to reduce professional isolation, allowing teachers to collaborate on practical solutions and share best practices (Little, 1990). This approach reflects the benefits of a "safe" and trusting environment where collaborative inquiry is encouraged and constructive feedback is welcomed (Louis, Marks, & Kruse, 1996).

Further emphasizing the role of collaborative practices, France discussed the importance of "utilizing collaborative learning models, such as Professional Learning Communities (PLCs) and Learning Action Cells (LACs)." These models align well with current trends in teacher professional development, supporting teachers in developing solutions collectively and fostering an atmosphere where they feel empowered to innovate and improve their instructional strategies.

Recent studies have highlighted the effectiveness of collaborative practices in promoting teacher empowerment. For example, a study by Zhang et al. (2020) found that collaborative professional development significantly increased teachers' self-efficacy and professional growth, particularly when opportunities for shared problem-solving were emphasized. This aligns with research by Phillips et al. (2021), which demonstrated that schools with strong collaborative cultures reported higher levels of teacher motivation and engagement, resulting in better student outcomes.

Den-Den also emphasized the value of creating an "innovative environment where teachers feel empowered to implement new strategies and share best practices," underlining the positive effects of collaborative innovation on teacher motivation and creativity (Stoll et al., 2006). Similarly, France added that fostering an environment where teachers feel "Fostering an environment where teachers feel empowered and confident." is crucial for driving professional growth. Furthermore, she highlighted the significance of "encouraging the use of technology in professional development to make learning more engaging and relevant."

In a recent analysis, Cavanagh et al. (2022) noted that when teachers engage in collaborative inquiry and share innovations, they not only enhance their instructional practices but also contribute to a vibrant school culture that fosters continuous improvement. Empowerment through collaboration not only enhances teachers' instructional abilities but also increases their sense of professional satisfaction and investment in their work. Research by Groves and Feyerherm (2020) supports the idea that collaborative environments significantly enhance teachers' perceptions of their professional identity and their commitment to ongoing development. By integrating structured collaborative practices and creating supportive environments, schools can enable teachers to take ownership of their professional development, ultimately leading to sustained improvements in teaching quality and student outcomes.

Subtheme 4: Positive Impact on Teaching and Learning

This subtheme emphasized the critical role that professional development (PD) plays in enhancing teaching practices, which in turn leads to improved student outcomes. Many teachers expressed that ongoing and well-structured PD initiatives equip them with the latest instructional strategies and methodologies, enabling them to create more engaging and effective learning environments.

As Den-den noted, "I look forward to seeing improved student outcomes," reflecting the positive expectations surrounding PD's impact. This continuous professional growth fosters not only individual teacher efficacy but also collective school improvement to translate teacher growth into student success. Research shows that targeted PD can increase student achievement, particularly when it focuses on strategies directly applicable to the classroom (Desimone & Garet, 2015). Effective PD experiences, then, have a dual impact—building teacher capacity while addressing students' learning needs (Borko, 2004).

Teachers also highlighted the role of PD in equipping them with skills they can immediately implement. Bob remarked, "Ma-successful pud ang mga teachers kung unsa na learn nila sa seminar or trainings na pwede ma-apply sa ilang klase para maging successful pud ilang mga bata," emphasizing the need for practical application. This perspective aligns with findings by Darling-Hammond et al. (2017), which suggest that PD programs focused on practical applications and job-embedded support are more effective in translating new skills into classroom practice. By allowing teachers to see the results of their efforts through improved student engagement and understanding, PD fosters a sense of professional accomplishment and reinforces a growth mindset.

The importance of ongoing support in the implementation phase of new strategies was also highlighted. Den-den added that providing "regular follow-up support to ensure that new strategies are effectively implemented in the classroom" is crucial for sustained application. This follow-up process contributes to a deeper integration of new skills, leading to more consistent instructional quality (Guskey, 2002). Continuous coaching and feedback ensure that teachers feel confident in applying new methods, which in turn maximizes the impact on students (Showers & Joyce, 1996).

Recent studies reinforce these findings. For instance, a study by Garet et al. (2020) found that ongoing, collaborative PD significantly improved teachers' instructional practices and positively affected student achievement. Additionally, an analysis by Avalos and Pons (2019) highlighted that when PD is perceived as an opportunity for growth, it fosters a more engaged and motivated teaching workforce, ultimately benefiting students. As Anton observed, "They (teachers) are now well-equipped with the knowledge and skills in manipulating computers that they may translate to their learners," indicating that PD can enhance technological competencies essential for modern teaching. Furthermore, a 2022 study by Kelly and Doran emphasized that teacher collaboration during PD leads to higher levels of implementation of new strategies and improved student outcomes.

This positive attitude towards PD fosters a culture of lifelong learning among educators, empowering them to take initiative in their professional growth. France noted the significance of this shift: "Creating a culture where professional development is viewed as an opportunity rather than an obligation, encouraging collaborative learning among teachers." Research by Tschannen-Moran and Barr (2020) supports this notion, showing that when teachers perceive PD as beneficial, they are more likely to engage actively and share insights with colleagues, enhancing the overall learning environment.

In summary, participants acknowledged that well-designed PD initiatives do not just enhance individual teaching skills but also have broader implications for student learning and the overall school environment. By cultivating a supportive culture around PD, schools can create lasting, positive effects that extend well beyond individual classrooms. Research conducted by Hymer et al. (2021) further illustrates that fostering a collaborative environment for PD leads to sustained improvements in teaching practices and increased student

engagement, solidifying the interconnectedness of teacher development and student success.

Subtheme 5: Tailored Support and Flexibility

This subtheme expressed a strong desire for professional development (PD) that is tailored to meet the unique needs of teachers within their specific contexts. This emphasis on customized PD underscores the recognition that one-size-fits-all approaches may not effectively address the diverse challenges and strengths present in different teaching environments. Participants noted that personalized PD opportunities can significantly enhance their engagement and motivation, as they feel more equipped to implement strategies relevant to their specific classroom situations.

France emphasized the importance of "anticipating tailored support systems that address the diverse needs of teachers," along with the need for "offering diverse formats for professional development, including online courses, micro-learning sessions, and after-school workshops." Additionally, she underscored the significance of "emphasizing the importance of ongoing dialogue with teachers about their needs, ensuring that support and development activities are aligned with what teachers genuinely require." Research supports the notion that effective PD is responsive and adaptive, taking into account individual teachers' strengths, challenges, and the particular demands of their teaching environments (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). Recent studies, such as those by Garbacz and Sheridan (2020), highlight that PD customized to address specific classroom and teacher needs enhances teachers' engagement and willingness to implement new strategies, fostering an environment conducive to sustained improvement.

Personalized support fosters a more engaging and effective learning experience for teachers, empowering them to implement new practices that align with their goals and the specific requirements of their classrooms (Desimone & Pak, 2017). This approach is echoed by recent findings from Aguilar et al. (2019), who noted that teacher satisfaction and commitment to PD initiatives increase significantly when PD programs are tailored to their immediate instructional needs and contextual realities. Den-den pointed out the value of "offering more tailored and hands-on professional development sessions," highlighting the necessity of practical applications and experiential learning during PD. Timperley et al. (2007) suggest that interactive and contextually relevant PD enables teachers to see immediate value and applicability, enhancing motivation and leading to sustained changes in classroom practice. Similarly, a study by Smith et al. (2021) found that hands-on training that includes real-world simulations and classroom applications significantly boosts teachers' ability to retain and apply new skills.

Anton stated, "I would like to recommend that schools be given leeway in devising their developmental programs." This aligns with findings by Borko (2004) and Darling-Hammond et al. (2009), who argue that flexibility in PD implementation allows schools to tailor content and delivery methods better to support teachers' specific needs and local educational goals. The importance of flexible PD has been further highlighted by Rivera-McCutchen and Watson (2022), who demonstrated that schools empowered to design their PD programs saw improved teacher satisfaction and enhanced professional growth.

By promoting autonomy in PD planning, schools can foster a sense of ownership and commitment among teachers, leading to a more engaged and responsive professional learning environment. Recent research by Wilson et al. (2021) suggests that when teachers have a role in shaping their PD, they are more likely to view it as meaningful, which in turn leads to greater engagement and willingness to innovate in the classroom.

In essence, tailored support and flexibility in PD offer teachers the tools and autonomy to refine their practice effectively. By adopting a differentiated approach to PD, educational institutions can create responsive programs that address the varied learning and professional needs of their teaching staff, leading to meaningful and sustained improvements in both teacher practice and student outcomes. This approach is reinforced by recent studies indicating that differentiated, flexible PD models contribute to stronger school communities and improved student performance (Knight, 2020).

Quantitative Interpretation of Results

In this section, the researcher presents the quantitative interpretation of results obtained from a survey conducted with 181 subject coordinators in the Schools Division of Escalante City. This analysis provides a comprehensive examination of the numerical data, offering insights into the perspectives and experiences of these educators. By applying statistical methods to the survey responses, the researcher aims to identify trends, relationships, and significant findings that contribute to understanding the role of subject coordinators in supporting teaching practices and professional development. The findings from this analysis will not only clarify the impact of subject coordinators on educational outcomes but also inform recommendations for enhancing their effectiveness in the educational landscape.

Extent of Teacher Support Provided by Subject Coordinators

This section examines the extent of support subject coordinators provide teachers, focusing on areas such as instructional guidance, resource allocation, and professional development. Table 1 presents the summarized results of the survey administered to 181 subject coordinators, highlighting mean scores and standard deviations across ten support indicators.

Table 1 demonstrates that subject coordinators provide a consistently high level of support across all indicators, with an overall mean score of 4.19, verbally interpreted as "Great Extent." Among the indicators, ensuring timely communication of important updates and

reports received the highest mean of 4.44 (SD = 0.717), signifying the importance placed on keeping teachers informed. This finding aligns with the work of DuFour et al. (2006), which highlights that effective communication fosters a collaborative school culture that empowers teachers and enhances their professional development.

Table 1. Mean and Standard deviation on the Extent of Teacher Support Provided by Subject Coordinators

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. provide guidance in the implementation of the curriculum	4.32	0.808	Great Extent
2. assist in aligning lesson plans with objectives, assessments, and tasks	4.24	0.909	Great Extent
3. monitor and ensure standards are met in teaching	4.18	0.879	Great Extent
4. assist in the preparation of instructional materials	4.15	0.904	Great Extent
5. assist in crafting assessments, aligning with competencies and table of specifications	4.22	0.890	Great Extent
6. assist teachers in utilizing assessment results for remediation and interventions	4.15	0.881	Great Extent
7. provide guidance on lesson delivery	4.09	0.959	Great Extent
8. give timely feedback after the lesson delivery to improve instruction	3.98	0.980	Great Extent
9. provide support and mentoring to newly hired teachers	4.14	0.944	Great Extent
10. ensure timely communication of important updates and reports	4.44	0.717	Great Extent
Overall Mean	4.19		Great Extent

Likewise, guiding curriculum implementation ($M = 4.32$), aligning lesson plans ($M = 4.24$), and assisting in crafting assessments ($M = 4.22$) garnered high means, emphasizing coordinators' efforts to maintain instructional quality and adherence to curriculum standards. As McLaughlin and Talbert (2006) observed, instructional leaders play an essential role in facilitating these aspects, which positively impacts student learning outcomes.

However, providing feedback after lesson delivery received the lowest mean of 3.98 (SD = 0.980) but remains within the "Great Extent" range. This result highlights an opportunity for improvement, as research by Hattie and Timperley (2007) underscores the transformative impact of specific and timely feedback on teaching practices.

Further evidence of the subject coordinators' active roles is reflected in qualitative responses, such as Participant 2's account:

"My role as a subject coordinator involves overseeing the curriculum for my subject area, and I provide guidance and assistance to my colleagues. I give them support by helping teachers with lesson planning. Sa lesson planning, ginaday-day namo if from the objective, aligned siya up to the assessment and assignment."

This aligns with the quantitative findings, showcasing the critical contributions of subject coordinators to lesson planning and assessment, which received high mean scores.

The results imply that subject coordinators play a pivotal role in fostering a supportive and productive teaching environment. Enhancing the feedback process and continuously refining communication channels could further strengthen their impact on professional growth and teaching effectiveness.

Extent of Professional Development Facilitation of Subject Coordinators

This section examines the role of subject coordinators in supporting teachers, focusing on the strategies they employ to address instructional challenges and promote professional growth. By analyzing the responses from 181 subject coordinators, the researcher aims to evaluate the breadth and effectiveness of teacher support initiatives, underscoring their contributions to enhancing teaching practices and fostering a collaborative learning environment.

Table 2. Mean and Standard deviation on the Extent of Professional Development Facilitation of Subject Coordinators

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. collaborate with the school head in conceptualizing and planning training activities	4.34	0.818	Great Extent
2. ensure professional development activities are created specifically to address the training needs of teachers	4.22	0.909	Great Extent
3. assist in the preparation of training activity designs that include detailed plans such as budget, rationale, and session objectives	4.08	0.897	Great Extent
4. facilitate School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions and In-Service Training on subject-specific topics	4.24	0.826	Great Extent
5. facilitate peer learning and collaborative activities to promote continuous teacher growth	4.21	0.810	Great Extent
6. ensure professional development activities are well-organized and implemented effectively	4.24	0.828	Great Extent
7. ensure that workshops and training sessions are focused on assessment, curriculum development, and innovative teaching.	4.17	0.879	Great Extent
8. ensure that sessions are focused on sharing best practices and student progress	4.26	0.846	Great Extent
9. invite resource persons and experts to provide valuable insights in professional development	3.85	1.010	Great Extent
10. integrate feedback from teachers to improve the relevance of professional development	4.16	0.877	Great Extent
Overall Mean	4.19		Great Extent

Table 2 presents the detailed mean scores and standard deviations on the extent of professional development facilitation. The data revealed that all indicators were interpreted to a "great extent," with the overall mean score of 4.19 signifying that subject coordinators consistently deliver effective support initiatives.

Notably, the indicator related to collaborating with the school head in conceptualizing and planning training activities received the highest mean of 4.34, indicating a strong emphasis on teamwork and shared vision in professional development initiatives. According to Leithwood et al. (2004), effective collaboration between school leaders and coordinators is essential for creating a culture of shared responsibility that fosters teacher engagement and professional growth.

Similarly, the indicators ensuring that professional development activities address the training needs of teachers (M = 4.22), facilitating School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions (M = 4.24), and ensuring that workshops focus on assessment and curriculum development (M = 4.17) also demonstrated high mean scores. These findings reflect a commitment to delivering relevant and effective training that aligns with educators' needs. As highlighted by Darling-Hammond et al. (2017), targeted professional development that is responsive to teachers' specific needs is crucial for enhancing instructional quality and promoting student learning outcomes.

This is further supported by Participant 4's response, who stated, "I usually prepare activity designs that include the rationale, budgetary requirements, training matrix, aims and goals of the activity including the training/session objectives." This statement emphasizes the thoroughness and intentionality with which subject coordinators approach professional development, ensuring that all necessary components are in place to achieve successful training outcomes.

Conversely, the indicator related to inviting resource persons and experts to provide insights received the lowest mean of 3.85, yet it still falls within the "Great Extent" category. This suggests that while coordinators are actively engaging external expertise, there remains potential for further enhancement in this area. This aligns with the work of Guskey (2003), who emphasizes that incorporating expert insights can significantly enrich professional development experiences and contribute to a deeper understanding of effective teaching practices.

Extent of Challenges Encountered by Subject Coordinators in Providing Teacher Support and Facilitating Professional Development Activities

The challenges encountered by subject coordinators in providing teacher support and facilitating professional development activities were examined. Key obstacles include time constraints, overlapping responsibilities, and resistance from teachers to changes and new systems. These challenges significantly impact the ability of subject coordinators to effectively implement teacher support initiatives and professional growth programs.

Table 3. Mean and Standard deviation on the Extent of Challenges Encountered by Subject Coordinators in Providing Teacher Support and Facilitating Professional Development Activities

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
In providing teacher support and facilitating professional development, I have encountered the following challenges:			
1. overlapping responsibilities due to multiple assignments or roles	4.09	0.917	Great Extent
2. limited time and conflicting schedules of teachers and subject coordinators	4.13	0.909	Great Extent
3. resistance of teachers to changes and systems introduced by the higher office	3.54	1.030	Great Extent
4. less tech-savvy teachers requires additional support with technology integration	3.58	0.989	Great Extent
5. limited teaching materials (e.g., bond paper, reproduction resources)	3.28	1.175	Moderate Extent
6. learning resources, such as textbooks, are insufficient	3.74	1.092	Great Extent
7. insufficient internet connectivity in the school to support teachers' professional development needs	3.71	1.176	Great Extent
8. lack of interest of teachers in producing desired outputs from the session	3.14	1.076	Moderate Extent
9. engagement of teachers in non - participative activities (e.g., watching shows) during the session	3.31	1.097	Moderate Extent
10. disengagement of teachers from professional development, arriving late or leaving early.	2.98	1.142	Moderate Extent
Overall Mean	3.55		Great Extent

Table 3 presents the mean scores and standard deviations on the extent of challenges encountered by subject coordinators in providing teacher support and facilitating professional development activities. The data indicate that several challenges occur to a "great extent," as reflected in an overall mean score of 3.55. Notably, the indicator related to limited time and conflicting schedules of teachers and subject coordinators received the highest mean score of 4.13, signaling that time constraints significantly hinder the ability of coordinators to provide adequate support and facilitate professional development. According to Bolam et al. (2005), effective professional development requires ample time for collaboration and planning; without this, the potential for meaningful learning is reduced.

Similarly, overlapping responsibilities due to multiple assignments or roles (M = 4.09) and resistance from teachers to changes introduced by the higher office (M = 3.54) also reflect significant challenges. These findings highlight the complexity of subject coordinators' roles, as discussed by Dufour and Eaker (1998), who emphasize that when educators are overwhelmed with multiple

duties, burnout and disengagement can result. Participant 6 raised this concern, stating, “But the problem is that they don't have enough time to meet. May timeline and overlapping activities.” This underscores the need for effective scheduling and time management strategies to improve collaboration between teachers and coordinators.

On the other hand, some challenges were encountered to a moderate extent, such as limited teaching materials ($M = 3.28$) and the lack of interest from teachers in producing the desired outputs from sessions ($M = 3.14$). These areas highlight opportunities to improve resource allocation and increase teacher engagement. Garet et al. (2001) stress the significance of quality materials and teacher motivation in boosting the effectiveness of professional development programs.

Moreover, the indicator regarding teacher disengagement from professional development, arriving late or leaving early, had the lowest mean score of 2.98. While this is still an area of concern, it does not appear to be as significant a challenge as others. This finding is supported by Penuel et al. (2010), who argue that fostering a supportive environment and setting clear expectations can improve attendance and engagement in professional development activities.

In summary, the findings emphasize the various challenges that subject coordinators face in supporting teachers and facilitating professional development activities. Addressing these challenges is essential for enhancing the effectiveness of instructional leadership and ensuring that professional development activities lead to meaningful outcomes for both teachers and students.

Extent of Opportunities Perceived by Subject Coordinators in Providing Teacher Support and Facilitating Professional Development Activities

This section explores the perceived opportunities available to subject coordinators in their roles of providing teacher support and facilitating professional development activities. Through an analysis of survey responses from 181 subject coordinators, the researcher aims to identify the strengths and resources that coordinators believe can enhance their effectiveness in these critical areas.

These opportunities may include access to professional networks, collaborative partnerships, and innovative training programs that empower coordinators to better assist teachers. By highlighting these perceived opportunities, this section underscores the potential for subject coordinators to positively impact teaching practices and professional growth within their schools.

Table 4. Mean and Standard deviation on the Extent of Opportunities Perceived by Subject Coordinators in Providing Teacher Support and Facilitating Professional Development Activities

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. provision of teacher support and professional development are sustained in schools	4.21	0.707	Great Extent
2. all teachers are given opportunities to be provided with support and attend relevant professional development activities	4.27	0.722	Great Extent
3. teacher support and professional development programs are aligned with real classroom challenges faced by teachers	4.25	0.795	Great Extent
4. flexible formats (online courses, after-school workshops) are offered for teacher support and professional development	3.94	0.932	Great Extent
5. subject coordinators promote peer observation, mentorship programs, and reflective practices	4.14	0.838	Great Extent
6. mentoring and coaching are integrated into the teaching load of the subject coordinator	4.04	1.013	Great Extent
7. subject coordinators provide follow-up support to ensure new strategies are applied in the classroom	4.13	0.884	Great Extent
8. teachers apply what they have learned from the subject coordinator to improve student outcomes	4.27	0.786	Great Extent
9. teacher support and professional development is viewed positively, as an opportunity rather than an obligation	4.28	0.748	Great Extent
10. sufficient resources (e.g., training materials, venue, internet) are provided to support professional development	3.94	0.893	Great Extent
Overall Mean	4.15		Great Extent

Table 4 presents the mean scores and standard deviations on the extent of opportunities perceived by subject coordinators in providing teacher support and facilitating professional development activities. The findings reveal that these opportunities are generally perceived to a “great extent,” with an overall mean score of 4.15. Notably, the statement regarding teachers being given opportunities to receive support and attend relevant professional development activities received the highest mean of 4.27, indicating a strong commitment to fostering professional growth among educators. This finding aligns with Guskey's (2000) research, which highlights that successful professional development must focus on teachers' needs and be perceived as beneficial for their growth and effectiveness.

Similarly, the alignment of teacher support and professional development programs with real classroom challenges faced by teachers ($M = 4.25$) indicates that subject coordinators are attuned to the practical needs of educators. This relevance is crucial for maximizing the impact of professional development, as noted by Opfer and Pedder (2011), who argue that effective professional development must be closely connected to teachers' daily experiences to be meaningful and impactful.

The provision of flexible formats, such as online courses and after-school workshops, received a mean score of 3.94, suggesting that

coordinators understand the importance of accessibility in professional development. Offering varied formats allows teachers to select options that best suit their schedules and learning preferences. Desimone et al. (2002) support this idea, emphasizing that providing multiple modes of professional development can enhance both participation and engagement.

Participant responses further underscore the significance of these opportunities. France, for example, emphasized the importance of “focusing on continuous learning opportunities, including peer observation, mentorship programs, and reflective practices.” This statement reflects the coordinators' recognition of the value of collaborative and reflective approaches to professional development. Peer observation and mentorship create an environment in which teachers share practices and learn from one another, aligning with Kraft et al.'s (2018) research, which indicates that targeted professional development can lead to improved teaching practices and better student achievement.

Moreover, the perception that teacher support and professional development are viewed as an opportunity rather than an obligation ($M = 4.28$) reinforces the importance of cultivating a positive culture around professional growth. Penuel et al. (2017) note that when teachers perceive professional development as an opportunity for growth, rather than a mandated requirement, they are more likely to engage actively, leading to greater benefits for both their teaching and their students.

In summary, the findings from Table 4 highlight the significant opportunities perceived by subject coordinators in providing teacher support and facilitating professional development. These opportunities are crucial for fostering a culture of continuous improvement and ensuring that teachers are equipped with the necessary skills and resources to enhance student learning outcomes.

Conclusions

The findings of the study revealed that while subject coordinators play a crucial role in supporting teachers and facilitating professional development, several challenges hinder their effectiveness. Coordinators reported issues with workload management, limited resources, and time constraints, all of which impact their ability to provide consistent support. Additionally, barriers in communication and a lack of structured training for coordinators themselves were identified as factors that may limit the quality and impact of their professional development initiatives.

However, the study also highlighted significant opportunities for subject coordinators to enhance their support for teachers. Coordinators recognized the potential for fostering a collaborative culture within departments, integrating digital tools for flexible training, and using data-driven approaches to tailor professional development activities. Aligning these activities with broader school improvement goals was perceived as a key benefit, maximizing the relevance and impact of professional development efforts.

Thus, the role of subject coordinators presents numerous opportunities to strengthen teacher support, improve instructional quality, and contribute to school-wide goals. Despite these promising prospects, the effectiveness of coordinators' support efforts faces challenges related to resource availability, role-specific training, and workload balance. Given the importance of subject coordinators in advancing teacher development and enhancing learning outcomes, addressing these challenges through structured support and resource allocation is essential. By doing so, schools can maximize the contributions of subject coordinators and ensure their integral role in fostering educational excellence.

Drawing from the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

To the Department of Education (DepEd). The Department of Education may establish regular training and capacity-building initiatives tailored to equip subject coordinators with essential skills in instructional leadership, coaching, and time management. This aligns with the study's significance in enhancing teacher support and instructional quality through well-trained coordinators. They may also allocate additional resources and create structured schedules that allow subject coordinators dedicated time for planning and implementing professional development activities. Providing adequate resources and scheduling flexibility directly addresses the study's findings on time and resource limitations faced by coordinators. They may also foster a collaborative culture across schools by setting up peer mentoring programs and team-based planning sessions. This recommendation supports the study's significance by encouraging teamwork and the sharing of best practices, enhancing instructional coherence.

To the School Administrators. The school administrators may develop data-driven professional development frameworks to assist subject coordinators in creating targeted training sessions based on teachers' needs and classroom observations. This directly aligns with the study's emphasis on using data to inform effective teacher support strategies. They may also promote alignment between professional development initiatives and school improvement goals to ensure that all professional learning efforts contribute to broader educational objectives. This recommendation aligns with the study's findings on the importance of cohesive and goal-oriented professional development activities.

To the Subject Coordinators. The subject coordinators may actively engage in ongoing professional development to stay current with instructional strategies, assessment techniques, and leadership skills. This recommendation supports the study's finding that continuous learning is essential for effective teacher support and professional growth facilitation. They may establish clear and open communication channels with teachers and administrators to ensure effective feedback mechanisms and timely updates on professional development opportunities. Enhanced communication, as highlighted in the study, fosters a supportive and responsive teacher-

coordinator relationship.

To Future Researchers. They may conduct longitudinal studies to explore the long-term impacts of subject coordinators' roles in facilitating professional development and supporting teachers, particularly regarding instructional outcomes. This recommendation aligns with the study's significance by contributing to the growing body of knowledge on the effectiveness of subject coordinator interventions in education. They may also consider qualitative methods, such as interviews and focus groups, to gain a more in-depth understanding of the experiences and challenges of subject coordinators in their support roles. This aligns with the study's aim to provide insights into the evolving role of coordinators in enhancing teaching quality.

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